

Mental Health Impacts in A World Disrupted by Climate Change

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ABSTRACT

In this brief commentary the author challenges social scientists whose research includes mental health to recognize that everything from the settings in which they work to the nature of their research is about to be disrupted by the impacts of climate change. The heart of this changing landscape includes the impacts that climate change will have on mental health, already in evidence among younger members of the population. Mental health research needs to incorporate climate change induced causal factors, shift its approach to a more iterative model and understand that socio-cultural, as well as psychological factors drive climate distress.

Keywords: *Climate change impacts; Mental health*

PERSPECTIVE

Linking Climate Change and Mental Health

Based on the findings of scientists worldwide there is every reason to believe that we will face a socially, politically and environmentally disrupted world over the next decades and that this disruption will profoundly impact mental health. Recent evidence presented by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change explicitly acknowledges the link between climate change and mental health, especially in young people (IPCC 2022). A ground breaking survey of 10,000 young people across ten developed nations published in Lancet reflects wide ranging emotional reactivity to the climate crisis correlated with perceived inadequate government response and associated feelings of betrayal (Hickman et al, 2021). Recently published Canadian research confirms these findings, including that young people feel betrayed by government inaction (Galway and Field, 2023). A consistent theme in these studies connects mental health issues such as anxiety and depression to a sense among young people that a climate change impacted future is uncertain and unpredictable and that societal leadership cannot be relied on to protect their well-being.

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Social Scientists Adaptation to a Socially Disrupted World

From the perspective of the frontline of responding to climate change and, in anticipation of a disrupted world, what adaptations are required of social scientists, particularly scientists whose focus includes mental health? Perhaps, the first and most significant adjustment is the most difficult – accepting that research and life in the community of researchers itself will be disrupted. Business as usual in the research and academic worlds by the second quarter of the 21st Century will become impossible. For example, at the time of revising this commentary the University of British Columbia branch in Kelowna was evacuated because of wildfires during the summer of 2023 (Kelowna Fire, 2023). In times of crisis such as war, societies typically redirect their resources to face the immediate threat (Klein 2020). Picturing an upsurge in climate change related mental health issues, researchers and academics will be called upon to design and evaluate immediate interventions on an emergent basis.

Reimagining Mental Health Research in a Socially Disrupted World

In anticipation of a physically and socially disrupted world, research programs and the institutions in which they are situated would do well to begin re-imagining themselves, even though the relatively cloistered environments of most universities have protected them from the initial impacts of climate change to date. The first evidence that universities were accepting the gravity of climate change was a proliferation of graduate programs in the environmental sciences (Borck & Coglianes 2009). However, mirroring the siloed response of many sectors of society many of these programs became highly specialized and began to occupy their own terrain quite separate from other faculties in universities. The specialized language of environmental sciences also makes its findings inaccessible to the wider society. For example, section A.1.2 of the recently released IPCC Summary for Policy-makers reads:

The likely range of total human-caused global surface temperature increase from 1850-1900 to 2010-20197 is 0.8°C to 1.3°C, with a best estimate of 1.07°C. Over this period, it is likely that well-mixed greenhouse gases (GHGs) contributed a warming of 1.0°C to 2.0°C, and other human drivers (principally aerosols) contributed a cooling of 0.0°C to 0.8°C, natural drivers changed global surface temperature by -0.1°C to +0.1°C, and internal variability changed it by -0.2°C to +0.2°C. {2.1.1, Figure 2.1 (IPCC 2023).

As the scientific evidence pointing to the cascading impacts of climate change, now and in the future, accumulated and extreme weather events worldwide became more frequent, interdisciplinary programs began to show up and recognize the social and cultural implications of climate change, including its intersection with social justice issues such as colonialism, racism and income disparity (Misiaszek 2012).

Covid-19: A Precursor of the Impacts of Climate Change

Covid-19 was a precursor of the impacts of climate change and an example of why responses to disruptive change are often delayed. The COVID-19 crisis provided us with a vivid example of how ‘not yet’ works. By early in January 2020 COVID-19 was in full swing in Wuhan, China but it was far away. Scientists and government intelligence agencies were frantically ringing alarm bells, but society after society in the developed world hesitated when action could have saved lives and prevented more dire economic consequences. The delay is exemplified in the timeline below:

- *March 7, 2020 – Canada’s Chief Public Health official, Theresa Tam reassured Canadians that Covid-19 was ‘low risk’ on.*

- *March 9, 2020 (the day before Italy locked down) – French President Macron strolled the Champs Elysees with his wife touting the vibrancy of the economy.*

We had to wait, to see it, to taste it, to hear the sirens blare and witness a loss of lives. And then we acted, some countries more boldly and definitively than others and with very different results.

Insensitivity to One Another and the Natural World

We are deeply attached to set of values and an economic system that have conferred tremendous material benefits while, at the same time, making us increasingly insensitive to one another and to those less fortunate, less privileged and less endowed, not to speak of our connection to the natural world (Ferguson et al, 2007; Henley, 2021). We tell ourselves that our good fortune reflects our virtue, our cleverness and the fruits of our efforts. The result is a trance like state of persistent self-interest, incessant activity and the pursuit of endless growth and progress that contributes to ignoring the cascading impacts of climate change.

The reticence of societies to wholeheartedly embrace the fundamental change that climate change demands of us is a critical area for research. How is it, future generations will ask, that knowing what we now know that we responded so slowly to the climate driven events that scientists are predicting? I remember vividly talking to some municipal officials about this. Their idea was that the majority of people do not have the *bandwidth* to address climate change in their everyday lives. By the time, they do their job, go to the gym, feed themselves, drive children to extracurricular programs and relax to some degree, there is nothing left over. Cultural theorist, Carolyn Pedwell adds another important dimension (Pedwell 2021). We are very much governed by habits and routines and it is only through the disruption of this highly patterned behaviour that transformation becomes possible. To this I would add that assumptions, beliefs and values *disappear* in habits and routines to the extent that we often don't know why we are doing things. In the meantime, the mental health impacts of climate change are in evidence and increasing, especially among young people, as noted in the studies cited above.

Emphasis on the Efficacy of Interventions

The further adaptation that climate change requires of the social science community is a shift in emphasis from a more purely scientific effort to get our understanding of mental health phenomena right at the outset to the more messy and iterative work of assessing the efficacy of interventions as we go along (Patton, 2011; Dozois et al, 2021). In the near-term future, the public health problems we will face are going to be too painful and widespread to hold back from intervening. We will need more precise and sophisticated developmental evaluation-focused research with the goal of evolving evidence enhanced interventions.

Socio-cultural Factors and the Etiology of Climate Distress

In conclusion, the etiology of climate change induced mental health issues poses some critical theoretical questions related to research and, ultimately, treatment. Clearly, a great deal of the mental anguish that young people are suffering originates in the uncertain future that climate change prescribes and their perception that society's leadership is failing to respond with commensurate urgency. The risk of understanding climate distress within the typical framework of mental health problems is to individualize what is fundamentally a socio-cultural and political problem. Arguably, conceptualization and treatment of climate change induced mental health issues needs to be firmly based in understanding the insanity of cultures that permit the destruction of environments that support life itself.

DECLARATIONS

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